

centration level in a variety of food stuffs. The conventional methods followed for determination of lead in food stuffs, comprise visual comparative colour developments with ammonium acetate, potassium cyanide and sodium sulphide or hydrogen sulphide in ammoniacal medium. However, these methods lack precision due to personal error. In this communication, an improved and precise method for determining lead in trace amounts by absorbance measurement, after eliminating the interfering inorganic and organic materials by standard methods is described.

Materials and Method :

Materials : All chemicals used were of AR grade. Carl Zeiss VSU2-P spectrophotometer was used for measuring the absorbance. Doubly distilled water over alkaline potassium permanganate in all glass apparatus was used throughout the experiments.

Procedure : Lead as lead nitrate was allowed to form a brown complex with potassium cyanide (1 ml, 10%) and sodium sulphide (0.5 ml, 10%) in ammoniacal medium (3 ml. ammonia, sp. gr. 0.91). The absorbance of which was recorded after diluting the contents to 50 ml. with water at 290 nm. Lead from 1-12 μ g per ml was found to obey Beer's Law. The amount of lead determined was computed from a standard calibration curve. Blank experiments were also carried out simultaneously under similar identical conditions. The results are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF LEAD

Lead (μ g)		Absorbance*	% Error
Taken Per ml.	Found Per ml.		
1.00	0.98	0.068	-2.00
1.50	1.52	0.10	+1.33
2.00	1.97	0.130	-1.50
3.00	3.03	0.20	+1.00
4.00	4.02	0.264	+ .50
6.00	6.02	0.382	+0.33
8.00	7.92	0.53	-1.00
9.00	8.91	0.585	-1.00
10.00	10.15	0.65	+1.50
12.00	12.15	0.90	+1.25

* Mean of five determinations.

All the studies were made at wavelength 290 nm and slit width 0.3 mm.

Total volume of the complex solution was always raised to 50 ml. in all the experiments.

Results and Discussion

From the observations, it is evident that the method developed may be suitable for determining lead contents in food stuffs in p.p.m. level after eliminating interfering materials. Various experiments performed show that excess of potassium cyanide (10ml, 10%), ammonia (10 ml, sp. gr. 0.91) and sodium sulphide (1 ml. 10%) have practically no effect on the absorbance of the lead complex.

It has, however, been noted that the complex decomposes on standing, and thus it is suggested that absorbance should be measured immediately after the complex formation or within 10-20 minutes.

An attempt was made to replace sodium sulphide by water saturated with hydrogen sulphide, which met with no success.

References

1. I.U.P.A.C. Commission for the determination of trace elements in food, *Pure & Appl. Chem.*, 1965, 10, 71.
2. E. F. DALTON and A. J. MALANOSKI, *J. Ass. of Analyt. Chemistry*, 1969, 52, 1035.
3. R. GAIEWSKA, M. NABRZYSKI and E. LIPKA, *Bromatol Chem. Toksykol*, 1976, 9, 1.
4. T. ZAWADZKA, *Rocznpanst. Zakl. Hig.*, 1976, 27, 411.

Polarographic Behaviour of *Cis-Trans* Isomers of Platinum(II) Complex of the Type $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)(\text{NO}_2)\text{Cl}_2]^-$

K. S. PITRE

Chemistry Department, University of Saugar,
Sagar-470 003, M.P.

Manuscript received 4 May 1979, accepted 29 December 1979

THE ligand arrangement around an atom after a substitution reaction may or may not be similar to that of the starting material even for inert complexes. The chemistry of Platinum(II) is exceptional in this respect, in that the product of a substitution reaction can be predicted with confidence. The *Cis* and *Trans* isomers of Platinum (II) complex having formula $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)(\text{NO}_2)\text{Cl}_2]$ have been prepared and examined polarographically. It is observed that each of the isomers gives a separate reversible cathodic polarographic wave. The value of $E_{0.5}$ for *cis*-isomer = -0.105V, Vs SCE and that for *trans*-isomer = -0.140V Vs SCE. In both the cases 1M KCl is used as supporting electrolyte.

Platinum(II) is a very well known ion for the formation of *cis-trans* isomers. In the case of Platinum(II) the product of a substitution reaction can be predicted with confidence.

The polarographic technique can be successfully employed for the identification of *cis-trans* isomers of metal complexes. Crow and Westwood^{1,2} have prepared the *cis-trans* isomers of Rhodium (III) and Cobaltic ions separately and got two distinct waves for the two forms of the complex.

The author has prepared the *cis-trans* isomers of Platinum (II) complex of the type $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)(\text{NO}_2)\text{Cl}_2]^-$ and examined them polarographically. The results of his observation are given in this paper.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of AnalaR/BDH grade. The solutions were prepared in conductivity water. An automatic pen recording C.I.C. (India) polarograph was used to record the polarograms. The pH of the solutions was measured using a Phillips pH-meter.

All the observations were made at room temperature, 27°.

The *cis* and *Trans* isomers of Platinum(II) complex of the type $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)(\text{NO}_2)\text{Cl}_2]^-$ were prepared³ and their polarograms were recorded⁴. The ionic strength and the pH of the solutions was kept constant; using KCl solution and a buffer solution for their respective adjustments.

Results and Discussion

It is observed that each of the *cis* and *trans* isomers of $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)(\text{NO}_2)\text{Cl}_2]^-$ gives a separate reversible cathodic polarographic wave. The details of the polarographic study are given below:

Supporting-Electrolyte	— 1M KCl
Maximum suppressor	— 0.001% gelatin
Platinum (II)	— $5 \times 10^{-4} M$
Ammonia	— $5 \times 10^{-4} M$
NO ₂	— $5 \times 10^{-4} M$

Drop time = 3.1 sec. Sensitivity = $0.3 \times 3, \mu\text{A}/\text{mm}$
 $\mu = 1.0$, Temperature = 27° and pH = 6.68 ± 0.2 .

TABLE I

1. $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)(\text{NO}_2)\text{Cl}_2]^-$ <i>cis</i>	$E^{0.5} = -0.105 \text{ V Vs SCE}$
2. $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)(\text{NO}_2)\text{Cl}_2]^-$ <i>trans</i>	$E_{0.5} = -0.140 \text{ V Vs SCE}$

The plot of $\log \frac{I}{I_d - I}$ Vs E for each of the two forms is a straight line whose slope is $54 \pm 1.5 \text{ mv}$ for the *cis* form and $56 \pm 1.1 \text{ mv}$ for the *trans* form indicating a reversible one electron reduction for both the cases. It is observed that for each of the two forms of the complex the polarographic diffusion current is proportional to its concentration and the Id/C value is 4.9 ± 0.2 for the *cis* complex and 5.6 ± 0.1 for the *trans* complex.

It is quite clear from the above data that the polarographic behaviour of the two isomers is sufficiently distinct for identification purpose. The *cis* isomer is reduced at a more positive potential than the *trans* form, which is an excellent agreement with results of Crow and Westwood who have reported a similar behaviour of *cis-trans* $[\text{CO}(\text{cn})_2(\text{NO}_2)]^+$ complexes. A qualitative explanation for the observed shift in the half-wave potential for the two forms is based on a simple electrostatic argument that the preferred orientation of the *cis*-complex is due to the large internal dipole at a positive surface.

Acknowledgement

The author is thankful to Prof. S. S. Nigam, Head, Chemistry Department, University of Saugar for providing laboratory facilities.

References

1. D. R. CROW, *Inorg. Nuclear Chem. Lett.*, 1969, 5, 291.
2. D. R. CROW and J. V. WESTWOOD, 'Polarography of metal complexes', Academic Press, London 1969, p. 154.
3. S. F. A. KETTLE, 'Co-ordination compounds', The English Language Book Society and Nelson, 1975, p. 40.
4. A. V. MAHAJANI and K. S. PITRE, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 97.

Non-equilibrium Thermodynamic Studies of Electrokinetic Effects. Part XIII. Relaxation Time, Entropy Production Studies in Ethylene Glycol Water Mixtures

R. L. BLOKHRA and S. K. AGGARWAL

Department of Chemistry, Himachal Pradesh University, Simla

and

V. P. SHARMA

Department of Chemistry, Panjab University, Chandigarh

Manuscript received 8 January 1979, revised 29 August 1979, accepted 31 December 1979

THE entropy production in irreversible processes such as transport processes (electro-osmosis in the present case) has attracted the attention of a number of workers¹⁻³. The character of entropy production, both in steady and non-steady state is now better understood in terms of non-equilibrium thermodynamics^{4,5}. According to Prigogine⁶, the entropy production is minimum in the steady state. However, the theory of minimum entropy production is valid only when linear laws and Onsager's reciprocal relations hold good. Glansdorff⁵ and Prigogine⁴ have given a new theorem which states that for both linear and non-linear